

ISic2833

I.Sicily inscription 2833

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.12.14 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Museo Mandralisca, inventory 1125

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331408

1. [έν ὀνόματι τοῦ πατρὸς καὶ]
2. τοῦ Χρι [στοῦ καὶ τοῦ]
3. ἀγίου πν[εύματος· ἐκοιμή]-
4. θη ἡ δούλ [η τοῦ κ(υρί)ου Ἰησοῦ]
5. Ἄσελλα [ζήσασα ἔτη —' ἡμέρα]
6. Κ(υρί) ου τῆ π [ρὸ — — — — —]
7. Νοβεν (βρίων) ἡ [— — — — —]
8. [ἐ]τῶν ν' Β[αλεντινιανοῦ καὶ Βικ]-
9. τορίου τ[ῶν λαμπροτάτων ὑπάτων].
- 10.

Edition: PHI332693

1. [έν ὀνόματι τοῦ πατρὸς κ(αὶ)]
2. [τ]οῦ Χρι [στοῦ κ(αὶ) τοῦ]
3. ἀγίου πν[εύμ(ατος) ἐκυμή]-
4. θη ἡ δούλ [η τοῦ θεοῦ]
5. Ἄσελλα σ [ύμβ(ιος) Κυρια(?)]-
6. κοῦ, τῆ π [ρὸ — — — —]

7. Νοβεν (βρίου) , ή [μ(έρα) — —]
8. [έ]τῶν νε' [ύπατία Ό]-
9. [ν]ορίου τ [ò —'].
- 10.

Edition: PHI334896

1. [έν όνόματι τοῦ πατρὸς κ(αί)]
2. [τ]οῦ Χρ ι [στοῦ κ(αί) τοῦ]
3. ἀγίου πν[εύματος· έκοιμή]-
4. θη ή δούλ [η τοῦ θεοῦ]
5. Ἄσελλα . [— — — —]
6. ΚΟΥ τῆ π ρ [ò — — —]
7. Νοβεν (βρίων) , ή [μ(έρα) — — —]
8. [έ]τῶν νε' [ύπατία Ό]-
9. [ν]ορίου τ [ò — — —].
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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